

Carbon sequestration by different ecosystem components

Akshay Sarkar¹, Bubai Bhakta²

¹Centre for Environmental Protection and Human Resource Development (KSI), B-10/289, Kalyani - 741235, West Bengal, India

²Research Institute of Molecular Genetics, Faculty of Agriculture, Kochi University, B200, Monobe, Nankoku, Kochi - 783-8502, Japan

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received– 10 August, 2017

Revised– 2 September, 2017

Accepted– 12, October, 2017

Available– 30 December, 2017

(online)

Keywords:

CO₂-emission

Global warming

Climate change

C-sequestration

Ecosystem components

Corresponding Author:

Akshay Sarkar

E-mail: akshaysarjar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Global environmental problems of global warming and climate change are primarily due to uncontrolled emission of green house gas (GHG), carbon dioxide (CO₂) in atmosphere. Various ecosystem components (plants, microbes, soil and water) in environment play important role to sequester the carbon (C) and minimize the problem. The literature considering the carbon sequestration properties of different ecosystem components is scanty. The present review attempted to draw a short picture on the carbon sequestration properties of different ecosystem components in environment as literature available. The present paper summarized the C-sequestration properties of higher plants (forestry, agroforestry, tropical and subtropical forests, medicinal plants and biofuel producing plants), algae, fungi, bacteria, soil and water to exhibit and elucidates their role in minimizing the problems of global warming and climate change and showed that variation in carbon storage among different tree species, other organisms and abiotic components. It can be concluded herein that ecosystem components play vital role in minimizing the CO₂-emission. Therefore, management and conservation of natural resources or ecosystem components in the environment is necessary to improve the control measures against the problem of global warming and climate change.

1. Introduction

Global warming and climate change are two serious problems in the present human civilization posing various adverse impacts in sustainable development (Bhakta et al. 2015). Unperfected and uncontrolled increment of green house gas (GHG), carbon dioxide (CO₂) in atmosphere is one of the major reasons of climate change. Atmospheric CO₂ concentrations are rapidly increasing and are expected to double in the next century (IPCC 2001). The atmospheric CO₂ concentration has increased by 40% from the pre-industrial level from 280 to 392 ppm by volume mainly due to the uncontrolled use of fossil fuel globally. It has proposed that approximately 1.5 – 4.0oC in mean global surface temperature will increase if atmospheric CO₂ concentration rises to about 700 ppm (Atwell et al. 1999).

Presently, scientists are worried about global warming and climate change, therefore, Kyoto Protocol and such a number of policies and various advanced researches have been under

taken in order to control the emission of CO₂ and minimize the CO₂ in the environment by the process of sequestration. Atmospheric enrichment of GHGs can be moderated by either reducing anthropogenic emissions, or sequestering C in plant biomass or the soil. Transfer of atmospheric CO₂ into other pools with a longer period, in such a manner that it is not re-emitted into the atmosphere in the near future, is called sequestration. Depending on the processes and technological innovations, there are three main types of C sequestration (Figure 1): (i) those based on the natural process of photosynthesis and conversion of atmospheric CO₂ into biomass, soil organic matter or humus and other components of the terrestrial biosphere; (ii) those involving engineering techniques; and (iii) those involving chemical transformations (Lal 2008).

From the view point of energy demand and sequestration of CO₂ in the form of energy, there is a great challenge to develop the feasible CO₂-sequestration method to reduce CO₂ concentration in the earth's atmosphere. In this respect, several technologies are developing using different

ecosystem components, plants, water and soils. Sequestration and conversion of CO₂ into green biomass is a natural and sustainable method to control the GHG related problems of global warming and climate change. Plants play important role to minimize the CO₂ in atmosphere by sinking and fixing CO₂ through photosynthesis and storing excess carbon as biomass. Due to this reason forests are major domain for sequestration and storage of atmospheric carbon on earth (above-ground and below-ground) by uptake, assimilation and storing as carbon-rich organic compounds such as cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin, starch, lipid and waxes, mostly in secondary woody tissues and in roots. Forest covers approximately 40% (5.1 Billion ha) of the land area of the earth's surface (FAO 1995), forms about 80% of all above ground biomass and about 40% of below ground carbon (Kirschbaum et al. 1996). Sea and inland water bodies have potential C sink properties by enhancing productivity (Bassi et al. 2014). In inland, wetland and wastewater have also potential C sequestration capacity (Kanungo et al. 2017, Bhakta et al. 2015). Many strategies have been developed in

controlling the CO₂ emissions from residential as well as commercial establishments and industries in order to minimize its effects on environment (IPCC 2005, Gough 2008). The CO₂ fixation by algae using water and wastewater bodies is one of the important technologies presently emerging as a sustainable approach for C-sequestration; i.e. sunlight being used to reduce CO₂ to carbon (Bhakta et al. 2015). Therefore, it is apparent that different flora, water, soil, etc. are playing a vital role in minimizing the CO₂ problem in environment.

The above discussion clearly revealed the unavailability of a concise literature considering the carbon sequestration properties of different ecosystem components (plants, microbes, soil and water). The present review attempted to draw a short and clear picture on the carbon sequestration of different ecosystem components in environment as literature available.

The followings are the sequential presentation of carbon sequestration of different ecosystem components:

Fig. 1 Strategies of carbon sequestration based on natural processes, engineering techniques and chemical transformations (Lal 2008)

2. C-sequestration of higher plant

Higher plants plays pivotal role in environmental C-fixation. Since, higher plants are capable to effective sequester and storage of atmospheric carbon in above-ground and below-ground biomass by way of processes of photosynthesis and growth (Mitra et al. 2015). Rate of biomass increase and hence rate of carbon sequestration vary from species to species of plants, with population density, environmental conditions, seasons, through rotation of a new plantation, integration of genetic, etc. Three major components (or sets of processes) together constitute net sequestration of carbon in forest trees:

1) Carbon uptake and assimilation, including immediate respiratory losses which detract from previously 'fixed' carbon in photosynthetic plant cells

- 2) Carbon transport, allocation and partitioning of carbon for storage, structural and metabolic use in above-ground and below-ground parts of the tree
- 3) Return of forest carbon to the atmosphere via oxidative pathways, notably via the food chain, biological decay and combustion of forest biomass and forest products.

C-sequestration in forest - Forest ecosystem plays important role in the global carbon cycle by sequestering a substantial amount of CO₂ from the atmosphere (Vashum and Jay Kumar 2012). Forest cover accounts approximately 40% (5.1 billion ha) of the land area of the earth's surface (FAO 1995). Globally, forests are a major carbon store and account for about 80% of all above ground biomass, and about 40% of below ground carbon (Kirschbaum et al. 1996). Kirschbaum et al. (2000) provides a comprehensive summary of global carbon pools and fluxes (Figure 2). Forests and woodlands

contain about 331 Gt of organic carbon in biomass, and forest soils another 656 Gt. These are significant portions of the global carbon pool in relation to the atmosphere (750 Gt), though orders of magnitude less than estimates of the large global reservoirs in the oceans (40,000 Gt) and fossil fuels

(>20,000 Gt). Establishing forest plantations on presently non-forested land provides an energy-conscious world with a clean, efficient means of absorbing some of the excess in atmospheric CO₂ (Borough et al. 1998).

Table 1 The list of some plant species and their C-sequestration and storage properties in different conditions

Plant species (local name)	C-sequestration		References
	Tonnes/ha		
	Premonsoon	Monsoon	
<i>Delonix regia</i> (Gulmohar)	4028.97	4142.46	Mitra et al. 2015
<i>Pistacia vera</i> (Pista)	1517.17	1546.06	
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Neem)	721.73	728.15	
<i>Peltaforum pterocarpum</i> (Radhachura)	631.77	640.30	
<i>Ficus religiosa</i> (Peepal)	245.81	248.85	
<i>Albezia saman/lebbek</i> (Raintree/Shirish)	132.04	136.37	
<i>Simarouba glauca</i> (Aceituna)	92.21	93.89	
<i>Grewia asitica</i> (Phalsa)	77.69	79.15	
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (chatim)	43.82	45.07	
<i>Mimusops elengi</i> (Bakul)	39.34	40.77	
<i>Cassia fistula</i> (Amaltas)	28.24	28.44	
<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i> (Pride of India)	5.55	5.94	
Tons/tree			
<i>Moringa olifera</i> (Madhashevaga)	15.775		Suryavanshi et al. 2014
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Neem)	12.272		
<i>Delonix regia</i> (Gulmohar)	12.247		
<i>Peltaforum pterocarpum</i> (Pilmohar)	9.576		
<i>Acasia nilotica</i> (Subabhule)	9.248		
<i>Delbergia sisso</i> (Sissam)	7.207		
<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Palas)	3.553		
<i>Albezia lebbek</i> (shirish)	2.419		
<i>Tectona grandis</i> (Teak)	1.915		
<i>Eucalyptus citriodora</i> (Nilgiri)	1.814		
<i>Anacardium excelsum</i> (espave), <i>Hyeronima alchorneoides</i> (Zapataro) and <i>Guarea grandifolia</i> (Cedro macho)	Together these three species stored an average of 21.6% of the C in the forest sites.		Kirby and Potvin 2007

C-sequestration of agroforestry environment- Agroforestry refers to the interface between agriculture and forestry. It is a sustainable land use practice where trees on farmland form an integral part of the farming system. Agroforestry is a dynamic, ecologically based, natural resources management system that, through the integration of trees on farms and in the agricultural landscape, diversifies and sustains production for increased social, economic and environmental benefits for land users at all levels (Leaky, 1997; ICRAF (2006). The dynamic natural resources of agroforestry system has significant role in C-sequestration. Kirby and Potvin (2007) reported that Avocado (*Persea americana*), orange (*Citrus sinensis*) and mandarin (*Citrus reticulata*) are all top-ranked C-sequester from which fruits were sold on local markets; these species stored an average of 16.9% of the C stored per ha in agroforests and represented 24.5% of agroforest individuals.

C-sequestration in tropical and subtropical plant species - Globally, forest Carbon sequestration is recognized as cost effective and efficient option to address the issues of climate change. Hence, the Reducing Emission from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) mechanism has been objectively functioning for this. The main priority of selection of REDD+ project is having large continuous block of forests. Specifically, Tarai region of Nepal is known as rich contiguous block of forests having high deforestation and forest degradation (DFRS 2014) which probably meet the targeted goal of REDD+ mechanism. Thus this study is conducted here in community and collaborative forests of Tarai region. The carbon sequestration refers to the capture or removal of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere and stores it in tree biomass (Jindal et al. 2008). As carbon sequestration importantly addresses the issue of climate change (García-Torres et al. 2013), it has a global concern under the reward policy (Muradian et al. 2012) of Reducing Emission from Deforestation and Forest Degradation

(REDD+) mechanism (Skutsch and Van Laake 2009). In fact, the live and dead trees store 60 % of the carbon in forest ecosystems. The avoided deforestation and forest degradation could globally generate worth of 1 - 4 billion t CO₂ potential (Mackey et al. 2013). Moreover, it could be doubled through afforestation, reforestation and sustainable forest

management. In addition, the tropical forests endow with natural insurance against many threats specifically drought, flood, and vector-borne diseases. climate change but keeping forests intact or expanding forest can contribute to mitigate and adapt against these risks.

Table 2 The list of some tropical and subtropical plant species and their C-sequestration properties

Plant species	C-sequestration	References
<i>Shorea robusta</i>	5.02 t/ha	Mandal et al. 2016
<i>Terminalia tomentosa</i>	5.14 ton	
<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	40.76 ton	
<i>Adina cordifolia</i>	9.31 ton	

C-sequestration of medicinal plant - Medicinal plants have a wide range of social, cultural and economic benefits to a large part of the Indian population (Ved and Goraya 2007; Vaidya and Devasagayam 2007) are widely used in India for various livelihood and health benefits. However, there is a lack of research on their carbon sequestration and economical potential in various carbon forestry schemes precluding farmers from potential carbon revenue opportunities. C-sequestration and economic potential of the selected three medicinal plant species have been described by the Aggarwal and Chauhal (2013) as follows (Table 3):

It is demonstrated that around 70% of the population in the country meets its health care by herbal medicine and it also contribute to the country's internal and external trade. About 10 billion out of 80 to 90 billion worth of products are exported. The global trade of medicinal plants is expected to rise to US \$ 7 Trillion by 2050, which offers good opportunities for the country. Therefore, the medicinal plant could be played vital dual roles in C-sequestration as well as in producing beneficial active biomolecule containing herb biomass.

Table 3 The list of some tropical and subtropical plant species and their C-sequestration properties

Name of plants	C-sequestration (ton C/ ha/yr)	Economic value (Indian Rupee) from carbon revenues	Reference
<i>Emblica officinalis</i> (Amla)	1	844	Aggarwal and Chauhal 2013
<i>Terminalia bellerica</i> (Behera)	2.64	1198	
<i>Terminalia chebula</i> (Harar)	1.42	2228	

C-sequestration of biodiesel plant - Biofuels reduces CO₂ emissions, because, it generates from C fixed biomass, releases lower amount of C than that of fossil fuel and uses the C of present C-pool. A wide variety of biomass feedstock is used for biofuel and bioenergy production, such as energy crops (e.g. miscanthus, jatropha, short-rotation copice); wastes (e.g. waste oils, food processing wastes); agricultural residues (e.g. straw, corn stover); forestry residues; and novel feedstocks (e.g. algae). *Jatropha* sp. is a plant commonly used in biofuel production (Wani et al. 2012). It can be successfully grown to rehabilitate degraded land, A 3-5 years *Jatropha* added 1450 kg C/ha and in fuel 230 kg C/ha/yr to soil. The added biomass each year recycled 85.5 kg N, 7.67 kg P, 43.9 kg K and other nutrients and improved microbial activity, available nutrients and water holding in soil (Wani et al. 2012). A 4 year plantation sequestered 2500 kg C/ha in soil and 5100 kg C/ha in biomass. *Jatropha* (Wani et al. 2012). Soybeans, Corn, Canola, Coconut, Oil Palm and Microalgae are also other potential C-sequestering plants used in biofuel production.

3. C-sequestration of algae

Recently, C-sequestration in fresh and sea water by algae especially micro algae is an emerging field. Various types

algae have been explored from environment and employed for cultivation for the production of biomass, which is used rich feedstock source for producing the biofuel (Bhakta et al. 2015, Lum et al. 2013, Lam et al. 2012). All the green plants, micro-alga, Cyanobacteria follow the Photosynthesis to fix CO₂. It is found that CO₂ fixing ability of micro-alga is 1.8 times greater than terrestrial plant. These micro-algae, cyanobacteria can also be used to produce bio-diesel, lipids, methane, hydrogen, amino acids etc. Thus, CO₂ fixation using micro-alga and cyanobacteria has been reported as an alternate solution. C-sequestration by algae in wastewater and by engineered algae for biofuel production has been reported by several scientists (Pittman et al. 2011, Tabatabaei et al. 2011, Mata et al. 2010, Moreira and Pires 2016). The major problems of this route are (i) the continuous mitigation of CO₂ from waste streams, (ii) low efficiency of open pond cultivation, (iii) resistance of micro-alga towards NO_x and SO_x and (iv) the feasibility at industrial level is not very certain (v) Photo-bioreactors are expensive. Bhakta et al. (2015) showed high CO₂ sequestration (53–100%; 150–291 mg/g) in wastewater with strong growth performance of high CO₂-tolerant microalgae isolated from wastewater. The table 4 represents C-tolerant, biomass production, C-sequestration and biofuel production properties of some algae and microalgae:

Table 4 The list of some elevated C-sequestering algae

Name of the microalgae	C-sequestration	Reference
A microalgal consortium of <i>Chlorella</i> sp., <i>Scenedesmus</i> sp., <i>Sphaerocystis</i> sp., <i>Spirulina</i> sp.	150–291 mg/g with 420 ± 0.43 mg/g biodiesel yielding capacity	Bhakta et al. 2015
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	55.3% and 80 mg/l /h	Cheng et al. 2006
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	11.73 mg /l/min	Eloka-Eboka and Inambao 2017
<i>Synechococcus</i> sp.	18.84 mg /l/min	Eloka-Eboka and Inambao 2017
<i>Hot spring algae</i>	Biomass production 0.2667 g/l/d	Skjånes 2007, Neogoro and Shioj, 1991, 1993
<i>Nannochloris</i>	Biomass production 0.350 g/l/d	Chiu and Kao 2011, Maeda
<i>Chlorococcum littorale</i>	Biomass production 0.044 g/l/d	Owada 1995, Sakai Sakamoto 1995
<i>Nannochloropsis</i>	Biomass production 0.300 g/l/d	Salih et al. 2011
<i>Chlorella</i> sp.	Biomass production 0.700 g/l/d	
<i>Cyanidium caladarium</i>	100% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Scenedesmus</i> sp.	80% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Chlorococcum littorale</i>	60% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Synechococcus elongatus</i>	60% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Euglena grasilis</i>	45% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Chlorrella</i> sp.	40% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Eudorina</i> sp.	20% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	15% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Nannochloris</i> sp.	15% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Chlamidomonas</i> sp.	15% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Tetraselmis</i> sp.	14% CO ₂ tolerance	
<i>Spirulina</i> sp.	It mitigates several hundred thousand tons of C emissions at below 10 Dollars /ton CO ₂ equivalent.	Ho et al. 2011

4. C-sequestration of fungi

Fungi are one of the important plant groups having potential impacts in C-sequestration. Many soil fungi consist of small, delicate hyphae that permeate a complex matrix of soil particles (Kathleen and Holder 2013). They are easily damaged, making it difficult to directly observe their activities under undisturbed conditions. Fungi are recognized

as soil microbes have the soil organic matter decomposition property by using fresh carbon as a source of energy, a phenomena called priming effect (PE). However, efforts to determine the consequences of this PE for soil carbon dynamic are in their early stage (Fontaine et al. 2011). Mycorrhizal fungi associated with plant roots may contribute to carbon sequestration in soils.

Table 5 Some bacteria of high C-sequestration properties

Bacteria	C-sequestration properties	References
<i>Bacillus schlegelii</i>	Carbonic anhydrase produced by <i>Bacillus schlegelii</i> . A maximum activity of 0.0453 micro mole /mil/min was observed at PH.	Muley et al. 2014
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	The optimum enzyme activity was found to be at PH 9. The enzyme activity showed decline with the increasing PH.	
<i>Serratia</i> sp. ISTD04	It contains unsaturated hydrocarbons approximately 58.06% and the total saturated hydrocarbon constituted approximately 24.57% with the remaining 17.37% accounted to other unrevealed species.	Thakur et al. 2017

5. C-sequestration by bacteria

The CO₂ fixing pathways are found to be operated in different aerobic and anaerobic microbes, such as bacterial, archaeal

domain and are called as extremeophiles (Table 5). These microorganisms are omnipresent in nature, having capabilities to flourish in severe environmental condition and can utilize CO₂ in different ways in the absence of solar

radiation and convert it into useful product. Various naturally collected mixed culture as well as engineered bacteria help in identification and characterization of microbes capable of CO₂ fixation. In a study atmospheric carbon dioxide sequestration is achieved with the help of carbonic anhydrase produced by *Bacillus schlegelii* and *Bacillus subtilis* showed maximum activity at pH 9 and 37°C (Muley et al. 2014).

A chemolithotrophic bacterium is also efficient in C-sequestration and biofuel production. The bacterial strain, *Serratia* sp. ISTD04, enriched in the chemostat in presence of sodium bicarbonate as sole carbon source was evaluated for potential of carbon dioxide (CO₂) sequestration and biofuel production. The mechanism of CO₂ sequestration of the bacterium was enzyme dependent, which are carbonic anhydrase and ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RuBisCO).

6. C-sequestration in soil and water

Soils, vegetation, wetlands play the major role in C sequestration of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Soil is one of the important store houses of C, since, it can sink a major part of the global C pool and contributes to increased biomass, improved soil health and function, including nutrient cycling, water infiltration, soil moisture retention as well as water filtration and buffering in wetlands. Globally, soils are estimated to contain approximately 1,500 gigatons of organic carbon to 1 m depth, more than the amount in vegetation and the atmosphere. Modification of agricultural practices is a recognized method of carbon sequestration as soil can act as an effective carbon sink offsetting as much as 20% of 2010 carbon dioxide emissions annually.

Natural processes of C-sequestration in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems are via soils, water, vegetation, wetlands. Soil contain a lower soil organic carbon (SOC) pool under managed condition, than their counterparts under natural ecosystems due to depletion of the SOC pool in cultivated soils. Soil C-sequestration enhances the concentration/pools of SOC. In temperate regions, loss of the SOC pool occurs in the first 20-50 years of conversion from natural to agricultural ecosystems and 5-10 years in the tropics (Lal 2001). In general, cultivated soils normally contain 50-75 percent of the original SOC pool. The depletion of the SOC pool is caused by oxidation or mineralization, leaching and erosion.

Seventy percent water body on earth is another important domain of C-sequestration. It comprises both inland and ocean water bodies. Aquatic plants, algae, microbes are the important components in sequestering the C. Wetland soil is an important carbon sink; 14.5% of the world's soil carbon is found in wetlands, while only 6% of the world's land is composed of wetlands. Ocean storage of C by injection is the important process of C sequestration. This process increases the concentration and pressure of C in water and is a stable and stationary pool of C. It significantly promotes the high growth of aquatic plants in ocean.

7. Discussion and conclusion

Increasing C-emission by anthropogenic activities is a global problem and reason for global warming and climate change. To control these problems, the investigation concerning the

C-sequestration has gained significant importance. Several studies reported the C-sequestration properties of various ecosystem components (abiotic and biotic) in order to evaluate their C-sequestration and storage proficiencies to minimize the problems of global warming and climate change. The present paper superficially summarized the C-sequestration properties of higher plants (forestry, agroforestry, tropical and subtropical forests, medicinal plants and biofuel producing plants), algae, fungi, bacteria, soil and water to exhibit and elucidates their role in minimizing the problems of global warming and climate change. It is also found that variation in carbon storage among different tree species, other organisms and abiotic components. It indicates that propagation and maintenance of high C-sequestering plants would a favourable solution in this regard.

From the critical appraisal of C-sequestration performance of all natural resources or ecosystem components as reported by various researchers, it can be concluded that ecosystem components play vital role in minimizing the CO₂-emission. Therefore, management and conservation of natural resources or ecosystem components in the environment is necessary to improve the control measures against the problem of global warming and climate change.

References

- Aggarwal A, Chauhal S (2013) Carbon Sequestration and Economic Potential of the Selected Medicinal Tree Species, Evidence From Sikkim. India. Journal of Sustainable Forestry 33, 59-72
- Andrew C, Eboka Freddie E, Inambao L (2017) Effects of CO₂ sequestration on lipid and biomass productivity in microalgal biomass production. Applied Energy 195: 1100-1111
- Atwell BJ, Kriedemann PE and Turnbull CG (1999) Plants in Action: adaptation in nature, performance in cultivation. Melbourne, Australia, MacMillan
- Bassi N, Kumar MD, Sharma A, Saradhi PP (2014) Status of wetlands in India: A review of extent, ecosystem benefits, threats and management strategies, Author links open overlay panel. Journal of Hydrology, Regional Studies 2: 1-19
- Bhakta JN, Lahiri S, Pitman JK, Jana BB (2015) Carbon dioxide sequestration in wastewater by a consortium of elevated carbon dioxide-tolerant microalgae. Journal of CO₂ Utilization 10:105-112
- Borough C, Bourke M, Bennett D (1998) Forests as CO₂ sinks - an opportunity for forest growers? Australian Forest Grower 21(1) Liftout Section 43: 1-6
- Cheng L, Zhang L, Chen H, Gao C (2006) Carbon dioxide removal from air by microalgae cultured in membrane photobioreactor, Sep Purif. Technol 50: 324-329
- Chiu YS, Kao YC, (2011) Microalgal biomass production and on-site bioremediation of carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxide and sulfur dioxide from flue gas using *Chlorella* sp. Cultures. Bioresource Technology 102:9135-9142
- DFRS (2014) Churia forests of Nepal. In Forest resource assessment (FRA), Department of Forest research and survey (DFRS), Ministry of Forest and Soil Conservation (MOFSC), Government of Nepal, Kathmandu, Nepal

- FAO (1995) Planning for sustainable use of land resources toward? A new approach, Sombroek WG and Sims D, Land and Water Bulletin 2, FAO, Rome
- Fontaine S, Henault F, Aamor A, Bdioui N, Bloor JMG, Maire V, Mary B, Revaillet S, Maron PA (2011) Fungi mediate long term sequestration of carbon and nitrogen in soil through their priming effect. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 43:86-96
- García-Torres L, Benites J, Martínez-Vilela A, Holgado-Cabrera A, editors. (2013) Conservation agriculture: Environment, farmers experiences, innovations, socio-economy, policy. Springer Science & Business Media, Dordrecht, the Netherlands.
- Gough C (2008) State of the art in carbon dioxide capture and storage in the UK: An experts' review, *Int. J Greenhouse Gas Control* 2: 155-168
- Ho SH, Chen CY, Lee DJ JL 2011. Perspectives on microalgal CO₂-emission mitigation systems--a review. *Change, Biotechnol. Adv* 29, 189–198.
- ICRAF: (2006) World Agroforestry Centre, Southeast Asia web site. (<http://www.worldagroforestrycentre.org/sea>)
- IPCC (Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change) (2001) *Climate Change 2001 Mitigation*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) (2005) *IPCC special report on carbon dioxide capture and storage*, prepared by Working Group III of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Metz B, Davidson O, Coninck HC de, Loos M, Meyer LA (eds.) Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, p. 442
- Jindal RS, Brent, Kerr J (2008) Forestry-based carbon sequestration projects in Africa: Potential benefits and challenges. *Natural Resources Forum* 32: 116-130
- Kanungo P, Kumawat DM, Billore SK (2017) Carbon Sequestration Potential of Constructed Wetlands used for Wastewater Treatment. *International Journal of Applied and Pure Science and Agriculture*. 3:4 DOI : 10.22623/IJAPSA.2017.3025.37RQP.
- Kathleen K, Treseder S, Holden R (2013) Fungal Carbon Sequestration, *Science* 339 (6127): 1528-1529, DOI: 10.1126/science.1236338
- Kirby KR, Potvin C (2007) Variation in carbon storage among tree species: Implications for the management of a small-scale carbon sink project. *Forest Ecology and Management* 246: 208-221
- Kirschbaum MUF (1996) The carbon sequestration potential of tree plantations in Australia. In : Bassi N, Kumar MD, Sharma A, Saradhi PP (eds.) *Status of wetlands in India: A review of extent, ecosystem benefits, threats and management strategies*, Author links open overlay panel *Journal of Hydrology, Regional Studies* Volume 2, November 2014, Pages 1-19
- Kirschbaum MUF (1999) Forest growth and species distribution in a changing climate, *Tree Physiology*, vol. 20, pp. 309–322
- Kirschbaum MVE, Fischlin A, Cannell MGR, Cruz RV, Galinski W, Cramer WA (1996) Climate change impacts on forests. In Watson RT, Zinyowera MC, Moss RH (eds.). *Climate Change (1995) Impacts, Adaptations and Mitigation of Climate Change, Scientific Technical Analysis. Contribution of Working Group 11 to the Second Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. pp 131-158. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge and New York
- Lal R (2001) World cropland soils as a source or sink for atmospheric carbon. *Adv. Agron.* 71:145-191
- Lal R (2008) Sequestration of atmospheric CO₂ into global carbon pool, *Energy Env Sci* 1:86-100
- Lam MK, Lee KT (2012) Microalgae biofuels, a critical review of issues, problems and the way forward, *Biotechnology Advances* 30: 673–690
- Leakey R, Simon A (1998) Tree domestication of indigenous trees in agroforestry for alleviation of poverty. *Agroforestry Systems* 38: 165-176
- Lum KK, Kim LK, and Lei XG (2013) Dual potential of microalgae as a sustainable biofuel feedstock and animal feed. *Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology* 4: 53
- Mackey BC, Prentice W, Steffen IJ, House D, Lindenmayer H, Keith S, Berry (2013) Untangling the confusion around land carbon science and climate change mitigation policy. *Nature Climate Change* 3: 552-557
- Maeda K, Owada M (1995) CO₂ fixation from the flue gas on coal-fired thermal power plant by microalgae. *Energy Conservation and Management* 36:717-720
- Mandal RA, Dutta IC, Jha PK, Karmacharya SB (2016) Carbon sequestration potential in community and collaborative forests in Terai, Nepal. *Tropical Ecology* 57(4): 655-662
- Mata TM, Martins AA, Caetano NS (2010) Microalgae for biodiesel production and other applications: a review *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 14: 217–232, 2010
- Mitra A, Bagchi J, Thakur S, Parkhi US, Debnath S, Pramanik P, Zaman S (2015) Carbon sequestration in Bhubaneswar City of Odisha, India, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*,4(8): 6942-6947
- Moreira D, Jose CM, Pires (2016) Atmospheric CO₂ capture by algae, Negative carbon dioxide emission path, *Bioresource Technology* 215, 371-379
- Muley P, Dhumal M, Vora D (2014) Sequestration of atmospheric Carbon dioxide by microbial carbonic anhydrase. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology* 8(11): 45-48
- Muradian RM, Arsel L, Pellegrini F, Adaman B, Aguila B, Agarwal E, Corbera B, Ezzinede D, Farley JG, Froger E, Garcia-Frapolli EG, Komez-Baggethun J, Gowdy N, Kosoy JF, LeCoq P, Leroy P, May PM, Peral P, Mibielli R, Norgaard B, Ozkaynak U, Pascual W, Pengue M, Perez D, Pesche R, Pirard J, Ramos-Martin L, Rival F, Saenz G, VanHecken A, Vatn B, Vira, Urama K (2012) Payments for ecosystem services and the fatal attraction of win-win solutions. *Conservation Letters* 6: 274–279
- Neogoro M, Shioj I (1993) Carbon dioxide fixation by microalgae photosynthesis using actual flue gas discharged from boiler. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology* 40:643-653
- Neogoro M, Shioj I (1993) Growth of Microalgae in high CO₂ gas and effect of NO_x & SO_x *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology* 1991:28:877-886

- Pittman JK, Dean AP, Osundeko O (2011) The potential of sustainable algal biofuel production using wastewater resources. *Bioresource Technology* 102: 17–25
- Sakai N, Sakamoto Y (2015) Chlorella strains from hot springs tolerant to high temperature and high CO₂. *Energy Conservation and Management* 1995:36:693-696
- Salih FM (2011) Microalgae Tolerance to High Concentrations of Carbon Dioxide, A Review. *Journal of Environmental Protection* 02(05). DOI10.4236/jep.2011.25074
- Skjånes K (2007) Bio-CO₂ – A Multidisciplinary Biological Approach Using Solar Energy to Capture CO₂ while Producing H₂ and High Value Products. *Biomolecular Engineering* 24: 405-413.
- Skutsch M, Laake PV (2009) REDD as Multi-level governance in Making, *Energy & Environment* 19: 831-844
- Suryawanshi, Patel MNR, Kale TS, Patil PR (2014) Carbon Sequestration Potential of Tree Species in the Environment of North Maharashtra University Campus, Jalgaon (MS) India
- Tabatabaei M, Tohidfar M, Jouzani JS, Safarnejad M, Pazouki S (2011) Biodiesel production from genetically engineered microalgae future of bioenergy in Iran, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 15: 1918–1927
- Thakur IS, Kumar M, Morya R, Gnansounou E, Larroche C (2017) Characterization of carbon dioxide concentrating chemolithotrophic bacterium *Serratia* sp. ISTD04 for production of biodiesel *Bioresource Technology* 243:893–897
- Vaidya ADB, Devasagayam (2007) TPA Current Status of Herbal Drugs in India: An Overview. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.* 41(1): 1-11
- Vashum KT, Jayakumar S (2012) Methods to Estimate Above-Ground Biomass and Carbon Stock in Natural Forests-A Review. *Journal of Ecosystem and Ecography.* (4). doi:10.4172/2157-7625.1000116.
- Ved DK, Goraya GS (2007) Demand and Supply of Medicinal Plants in India, NMPB, New Delhi & FRLHT, Bangalore, India
- Wani SP, Chander G, Sahrawat KL, Rao SC, Raghvendra G, Susanna P (2012) Carbon sequestration and land rehabilitation through *Jatropha curcas* (L.) plantation in degraded lands. *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 161:112– 120